

PROBABILISTIC MODELLING OF THE PROCESS INDUCED VARIATIONS IN PULTRUSION

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1 General Introduction

Manufacturing processes introduce several sources of uncertainties into the material properties as well as the dimensions of the final product. Hence, stochastic modeling of manufacturing processes has a great potential to improve the understanding of the variation in the final properties owing to the inherent uncertainties in the process. In this respect, instead of having a purely deterministic model, a stochastic model is used in combination with a deterministic model for the simulation of the pultrusion process in the present paper. Pultrusion is a continuous and a cost effective composite manufacturing process in which constant cross sectional profiles are produced. Since the pultruded profiles are foreseen to be used more frequently in several industries such as construction, wind energy etc., it is necessary to take the uncertainties coming from the pultrusion process into account to evaluate the level of variation of the desired final properties or dimensions of the product. A schematic view of the pultrusion process is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic view of a pultrusion process. The fibers and the matrix material are pulled through a heating die via a pulling system. At the end of the process the product is cut into the desired length.

In order to improve the product quality or increase the productivity of the process, a detailed understanding of the process characteristics such as temperature profiles, curing and mechanical behavior is required. In the literature, several deterministic studies [1-9] and probabilistic studies [10, 11] have been carried out for the thermo-chemical simulation of the pultrusion process. However, these references provide no information about the sensitivity of the mechanical response such as residual stresses and distortions with respect to variations in the process conditions and material parameters in pultrusion. The residual stresses and distortions arise in the composite manufacturing processes due to a number of different mechanisms [12-15]: (i) the mismatch in the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the matrix material and the fibers, (ii) the chemical shrinkage of the matrix material, (iii) the tool-part interaction and (iv) the temperature and the degree of cure gradients through the composite thickness due to non-uniform curing. Apart from the pultrusion process, probabilistic analyses of other composite manufacturing processes, particularly resin transfer molding (RTM), have been carried out by several researchers [16-19]. In [18], the probability of the process-induced deformations of a composite part exceeding a specified allowable tolerance was calculated by using the first order reliability method (FORM). In [19], the reliability assessment of the process temperature and the cure degree were investigated based on the random variables by using the FORM.

The present paper investigates the effects of uncertainties in the pultrusion process parameters

(e.g. thermal and mechanical properties, fiber volume ratio, pulling speed, heater temperatures, etc.) on the process induced variations. This has not been considered in the literature up to now for this specific application (i.e. the thermo-chemical-mechanical modeling of pultrusion). The residual stresses and distortions of a pultruded unidirectional (UD) glass/epoxy square profile are predicted using a coupled 3D Eulerian thermo-chemical model together with a 2D quasi-static Lagrangian plane strain mechanical model [8]. Two different case studies are considered in which different expressions for the rate of cure and the resin elastic modulus development are used. This is done in order to investigate what the choice of these models means for the pultrusion process simulation. For the probabilistic analysis, Monte Carlo Simulations (MCS) with the Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) technique have been performed by evaluating the aforementioned coupled 3D/2D deterministic thermo-chemical-mechanical models. This approach gives a better understanding of the effect of the variations inherently involved in the process and makes it easier or more practical to predict how large and sensitive the scatter of the output parameters with respect to scatter in the input design parameters are.

2 Numerical Implementation

2.1 Thermo-chemical Model

The energy equations given in Eq. 1 (for the composite part) and Eq. 2 (for the die) are solved in the deterministic 3D thermo-chemical simulation of the pultrusion process.

$$\rho_c C p_c \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_3} \right) = k_{x_1,c} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_1^2} + k_{x_2,c} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_2^2} + k_{x_3,c} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_3^2} + q \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_d C p_d \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_{x_1,d} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_1^2} + k_{x_2,d} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_2^2} + k_{x_3,d} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_3^2} \quad (2)$$

where T is the temperature, t is the time, u is the pulling speed, ρ is the density, Cp is the specific

heat and k_{x1} , k_{x2} and k_{x3} are the thermal conductivities along x_1 , x_2 and x_3 directions, respectively. The subscriptions c and d correspond to composite and die, respectively. Lumped material properties are used and assumed to be constant. The internal heat generation (q) [W/m^3] due to the exothermic reaction of the epoxy resin can be expressed as [6]:

$$q = (1 - V_f) \rho_r H_{tr} R_r(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

where V_f is the fiber volume fraction and H_{tr} is the total heat of reaction, ρ_r is the density of epoxy resin, α is the degree of cure.

In the present study, two different cure rate expressions (i.e. $R_r(\alpha) = d\alpha/dt$), which are given in Eq. 4 and Eq. 5, are considered.

Model-1 [6]:

$$R_r(\alpha) = K_o \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

Model-2 [8, 15]:

$$R_r(\alpha) = K_o \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) (1 - \alpha)^n \cdot f(\alpha, T) \quad (5)$$

where K_o is the pre-exponential constant, E is the activation energy, R is the universal gas constant and n is the order of reaction (kinetic exponent) [6]. In Eq. 5, $f(\alpha, T)$ is the diffusion factor which accounts for the glass transition effect defined as [15]:

$$f(\alpha, T) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[C(\alpha - (\alpha_{c0} + \alpha_{cT}))]} \quad (6)$$

where C is a diffusion constant, α_{c0} is the critical degree of cure at $T = 0$ K and α_{cT} is a constant for the increase in critical α with T [15]. Due to the material movement inside the die the resin kinetics equation can be expressed as [8]

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = R_r(\alpha) - u \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x_3} \quad (7)$$

where it is the expression in Eq. 7 which is used in the numerical model. For the thermo-chemical

simulation of the pultrusion process, the control volume based finite difference (CV/FD) method [1, 4, 10, 20] is used in order to obtain the temperature and degree of cure distributions. MATLAB [21] is used for the implementation of the CV/FD.

2.2 Thermo-chemical-mechanical Model

As earlier mentioned, the instantaneous resin elastic modulus (E_r) development during the process is calculated using two different approaches. The corresponding expressions for the resin elastic modulus are given in Eq. 8 and Eq. 9.

Model-1 [14]: Cure dependent resin modulus

$$E_r = (1 - \alpha)E_{r0} + \alpha E_{r\infty} \quad (8)$$

Model-2 [15]: Cure and temperature dependent resin modulus (cure hardening instantaneous linear elastic (CHILE) approach)

$$E_r = \begin{cases} E_{r0} & T^* < T_{C1} \\ E_{r0} + E_r^* & \text{for } T_{C1} \leq T^* \leq T_{C2} \\ E_{r\infty} & T^* > T_{C2} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$E_r^* = \frac{T^* - T_{C1}}{T_{C2} - T_{C1}} (E_{r\infty} - E_{r0})$$

where E_{r0} and $E_{r\infty}$ are the uncured and fully cured resin moduli, respectively. T_{C1} and T_{C2} are the critical temperatures at the onset and completion of the glass transition, respectively, T^* represents the

difference between the instantaneous resin glass transition temperature (T_g) and the resin temperature, i.e. $T^* = T_g - T$ [15]. The evolution of the T_g with the degree of cure is modeled by the Di Benedetto equation [15]. The linear elastic CHILE approach includes the cure hardening and also thermal softening [15] and it is suitable for pultrusion since shorter process times are present here as compared to other composite manufacturing processes such as RTM, Vacuum Infusion and Autoclave processes.

The effective mechanical properties of the composite are calculated by using the SCFM approach which is a well known technique in the literature [8, 14]. User-subroutines in ABAQUS [22] are used for the calculation of the residual stresses and distortions as used in [8, 9, 14].

3 Deterministic Analysis of the Pultrusion Process

3.1 Problem Description

The 3D thermo-chemical simulation of the pultrusion of a square profile, in which the temperature and degree of cure distributions are calculated, is carried out in a Eulerian frame. A UD glass/epoxy based composite and a steel die are used for the composite and the die block, respectively. Material properties and the resin kinetic parameters are listed in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. The parameters used for the diffusion factor (Eq. 6) are given in Table 2. Only a quarter of the pultrusion domain, seen in Fig. 2, is modelled due to symmetry. At the symmetry surfaces adiabatic boundaries are

Table 1. Material Properties [6].

Material	ρ (kg/m ³)	C_p (J/kg K)	k_{x_3} (W/m K)	k_{x_1}, k_{x_2} (W/m K)
Composite ($V_f = 63.9\%$)	2090.7	797.27	0.9053	0.5592
Die	7833	460	40	40

Table 2. Epoxy Resin Kinetic Parameters [6, 8].

H_{tr} [kJ/kg]	K_0 [1/s]	E [kJ/mol]	N	C	α_{C0}	α_{CT} [1/K]
324	192000	60	1.69	30	-1.5	0.0055

defined in which no heat flow is allowed across the boundaries. The remaining exterior surfaces of the die are exposed to ambient temperature (27 °C) with a convective heat transfer coefficient of 10 W/(m² K) except for the surfaces located at the heating regions. Similarly, at the post die region, convective boundaries are defined for the exterior surfaces of the pultruded profile. The length of the post die region (L_{conv} in Fig. 2) is determined to be approximately 9.2 m.

In the mechanical analysis of the process, the calculated temperature and degree of cure profiles in 3D are transferred to a 2D quasi-static analysis and the corresponding stresses, strains and displacements are calculated accordingly in ABAQUS. The details of this approach are given in Fig. 3. In the 2D thermo-chemical-mechanical simulation, a plane strain assumption is made [8] and a realistic mechanical contact formulation at the die-part interface, which allows separation of the composite from the rigid die surface due to the shrinkage of the part, is defined.

Fig. 2. Schematic view of the pultrusion domain and the cross-sectional details of the pultruded profile.

All dimensions are in mm. Not to scale.

Two case studies are carried out in which the expressions for the resin kinetics ($R(\alpha)$) and the instantaneous resin elastic modulus (E_r) are varied. The summary of these models are given in Table 3. In Model-1, Eq. 4 and Eq. 8 and in Model-2, Eq. 5 and Eq. 9 are used for the calculation of $R_r(\alpha)$ and E_r , respectively. It should be noted that the resin coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in rubbery state ($T_g < T$) is known to be approximately 2.5

times of the CTE in glassy state ($T_g > T$) [12]. In the present work, the change in T_g is only taken into account for Model-2. The constants for the CHILE model and the Di Benedetto equation together with the mechanical properties of the epoxy resin and the fibers in Model-2 are taken from [8]. In the present study, the total volumetric shrinkage of the epoxy resin is assumed to be 6% for both models (Model-1 and Model-2) [8].

Fig. 3. Representation of the coupling of the 3D Eulerian thermo-chemical model with the 2D Lagrangian plain-strain mechanical model [8].

Table 3. Summary of the two different models used in the present study

	Model-1	Model-2
Resin Kinetics ($R_r(\alpha)$)	Eq. 4	Eq. 5
Instantaneous resin modulus (E_r)	Eq. 8	Eq. 9

3.2 Results and Discussion

The calculated temperature and degree of cure distributions at the interior region of the part (point A) are depicted in Fig. 4 for the two different models (Model-1 and Model-2, see Table 3). It is seen that there is a very small difference in temperature distributions between these two models. The degree of cure increases for both models at the post die region, however this increase is relatively smaller in

Model-2 as compared to Model-1 since the diffusion factor (Eq. 6) used in Model-2 slows down the curing after vitrification ($T_g > T$) owing to the switch of the resin reaction from a kinetic form to a diffusive form [15]. As a result, a relatively higher degree of cure at the end of the process ($\alpha = 0.98$) is obtained at the center of the product (point A) for Model-1 as compared to Model-2 ($\alpha = 0.97$).

Fig. 4. Temperature (*top*) and degree of cure (*bottom*) distributions at point A (center of the composite) for Model-1 and Model-2.

Fig. 5. Displacement evolutions at point B in x_2 -direction (U_2). Triangular mark indicates the glass transition for Model-2.

The evolution of the process induced transverse normal stresses in the x_1 -direction (S_{11}) are shown in Fig. 6. A similar trend for the stress development during the process is obtained as in [8] such that tension stresses prevail at the inner region (point A) and compression stresses occurs at the outer region (point B). It is found that relatively higher stress levels are obtained for Model-1 as compared to Model-2. In Model-1, stresses start developing after curing takes place (at approximately 0.4 m, see Fig. 5) because at the same time the part starts getting stiffness due to the cure dependent resin modulus in Model-1. In Model-2, the stress levels decrease after T_g because, as earlier mentioned, the CTE of the epoxy resin in rubbery state ($T_g < T$) is known to be approximately 2.5 times of the CTE in glassy state ($T_g > T$) [12]. The corresponding undeformed contour plots of S_{11} at the end of the process (i.e. at $x_3 \approx 10$ m) are shown in Fig. 7. The maximum compression stress S_{11} at point B is calculated to be approximately -22 MPa (Fig. 7a) and -13 MPa (Fig. 7b) for Model-1 and Model-2, respectively. On the other hand, the maximum tension stress S_{11} at point A is found to be approximately 9.5 MPa (Fig. 7a) and 3.3 MPa (Fig. 7b) for Model-1 and Model-2, respectively.

Fig. 6. The transverse process induced stress (S11) development at point B (left) and at point A (right) using Model-1 and Model-2.

Fig. 7. Undeformed contour plots of the residual stress at the end of the process for Model-1 (a) and Model-2 (b).

4 Probabilistic Analysis of Pultrusion Process

4.1 Description of the Probabilistic Model

The uncertainties in the processing parameters and material properties of the pultruded part are defined as random input parameters (RIPs). A total of 29 RIPs with a Gaussian distribution are considered in the probabilistic analysis of the pultrusion process and Table 4 summarizes these RIPs. Here, ‘GAUSS’ denotes the Gaussian (Normal) distribution with mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) where $\sigma = \mu \times \text{COV}$. In general, the statistical characteristics are obtained from the extensive data collection and data

analysis. In the present study, the mean values of the RIPs are taken from the deterministic analysis carried out in Section 3 and the standard deviations are estimated based on engineering intuition and common available data from the literature [10, 11, 19]. Here, the 4th random variable, namely the heater temperature multiplier (“*cons*”), is defined as a multiplier for all three heater temperatures. For instance, the temperature of the first heater becomes a random variable by multiplying it with a random parameter, i.e. *cons*. Hence, it has a normal distribution with a mean (μ) of 171 °C and a standard deviation (σ) of $171 \times 0.02 \approx 3.4$ °C. The

Table 4. The random variables and their statistical characterizations for the pultrusion process.

Nr.	Property	Symbol	Unit	μ	COV	Distribution
1	Pulling speed	u	cm/min	20	0.02	GAUSS
2	Fiber volume ratio	V_f	-	0.639	0.02	GAUSS
3	Inlet temperature	T_{left}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	30	0.02	GAUSS
4	Heater Temperature multiplier	$cons$	-	1	0.02	GAUSS
5	Density of resin	ρ_r	kg/m^3	1260	0.05	GAUSS
6	Density of fiber	ρ_f	kg/m^3	2560	0.05	GAUSS
7	Specific heat of resin	Cp_r	J/kg K	1255	0.05	GAUSS
8	Specific heat of fiber	Cp_f	J/kg K	670	0.05	GAUSS
9	Thermal conductivity of resin	k_r	W/m K	0.21	0.05	GAUSS
10	Transverse thermal conductivity (fiber)	$(k_{x1})_f$	W/m K	1.04	0.05	GAUSS
11	Longitudinal thermal conductivity (fiber)	$(k_{x3})_f$	W/m K	11.4	0.05	GAUSS
12	Total heat of reaction	H_{tr}	J/kg	3.24e5	0.02	GAUSS
13	Pre-exponential constant	K_0	1/s	1.92e5	0.02	GAUSS
14	Activation energy	E	J/mol	6.0e4	0.02	GAUSS
15	Order of reaction	N	-	1.69	0.02	GAUSS
16	Uncured resin modulus	E_{r0}	MPa	3.447	0.05	GAUSS
17	Fully cured resin modulus	$E_{r\infty}$	MPa	3.447e3	0.05	GAUSS
18	Poisson's ratio of resin	ν_r	-	0.35	0.05	GAUSS
19	Longitudinal fiber modulus	E_{33f}	MPa	7.308e4	0.05	GAUSS
20	Transverse fiber modulus	E_{11f}	MPa	7.308e4	0.05	GAUSS
21	Longitudinal Poisson's ration of fiber	ν_{31f}	-	0.22	0.05	GAUSS
22	Transverse Poisson's ration of fiber	ν_{12f}	-	0.22	0.05	GAUSS
23	Longitudinal shear modulus of fiber	G_{31f}	MPa	2.992e4	0.05	GAUSS
24	Transverse shear modulus of fiber	G_{12f}	MPa	2.992e4	0.05	GAUSS
25	Total volumetric shrinkage of the resin	V_{sh}	-	0.06	0.05	GAUSS
26	Longitudinal CTE of fiber	α_{33f}	1/ K	5.04e-6	0.05	GAUSS
27	Transverse CTE of fiber	α_{11f}	1/ K	5.04e-6	0.05	GAUSS
28	Longitudinal CTE of resin	α_{33r}	1/ K	5.76e-5	0.05	GAUSS
29	Transverse CTE of resin	α_{11r}	1/ K	5.76e-5	0.05	GAUSS

same approach is also valid for the other two heater temperatures.

The transverse stress (S11) at point B predicted at the end of the process (See Fig. 7) is taken as the random output response (ROR) since the maximum stress level is obtained at that point. In addition, the displacement of point B in the transverse direction (U2) after cooling to ambient temperature is also defined as a ROR.

The MCS with LHS technique is used to evaluate the cumulative distribution functions of the RORs together with corresponding linear correlation coefficients between the RIPS and the RORs which indicates the sensitivity of each RIPS with respect to

the defined RORs. A total of 1,000 MCS are performed for each thermo-chemical-mechanical models (i.e. Model-1 and Model-2, see Table 3).

4.2 Results and Discussion

The cumulative distribution functions of S11 and U2 for point B at the end of the process are given in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively. It is seen that using the same RIPS in both models (Model-1 and Model-2), different sampling trends are obtained, i.e. the sampling range is relatively wider in Model-1 as compared to Model-2. The probability values indicate the probability of S11 (Fig. 8) or U2 (Fig. 9) being below that particular level. For instance, based on the RIPS (Table 4), the probability of S11 being

larger (in compression) than -30 MPa is 1% for Model-1 and for Model-2 the probability of S11 being larger than -15.3 MPa is approximately 2%. Similarly, the probability of U2 being larger than -1.4×10^{-4} m (in magnitude) is approximately 8% for Model-1 and probability of U2 being larger than -0.9×10^{-4} m is approximately 2% for Model-2.

The corresponding linear correlation coefficients are depicted in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 for Model-1 and Model-2, respectively. The sensitivities of the RIPs are shown as a pie chart and a bar plot for the RORs, i.e. S11 and U2, for the two models. For Model-1, it is seen from Fig. 10 that the most sensitive parameter is found to be the total volumetric shrinkage of the resin (V_{sh}) which has a negative correlation coefficient of around -0.7. A negative correlation indicates that an increase in the input parameter provides a decrease in the output parameter and vice versa, e.g. if V_{sh} increases, the values of S11 and U2, which are negative, decreases or the magnitude of them increases as expected by using Model-1. On the other hand, the most sensitive parameter is found to be the fully cured resin modulus ($E_{r\infty}$) and the fiber volume ratio (V_f) for S11 and U2, respectively, by using Model-2. It should be noted that the variation in V_f has also an important effect on the output parameter U2 which has a correlation coefficient of around 0.6 for Model-1. Similarly, it is seen from Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 that the effect of the variation in the V_f on S11 is less than on U2 for both models. On the other hand, the variation in $E_{r\infty}$ has a more important effect on S11 as compared to U2.

Fig. 8. Gauss plot of the cumulative distribution function of S11 at point B at the end of the process using Model-1 and Model-2.

Fig. 9. Gauss plot of the cumulative distribution function of U2 at point B at the end of the process using Model-1 and Model-2.

Fig. 10. The linear correlation coefficients between the RIPs and S11 (top); and U2 (bottom) at point B in bar plot and corresponding sensitivities in pie chart for Model-1.

Fig. 11. The linear correlation coefficients between the RIPs and S11 (top); and U2 (bottom) at point B in bar plot and corresponding sensitivities in pie chart for Model-2.

Conclusions

In this study the application of the MCS with LHS technique for the probabilistic simulation of the pultrusion process was investigated based on the process induced variations such as residual stresses and distortions. Two different material models (see Table 3) were considered in the 3D/2D deterministic thermo-chemical-mechanical simulation of the process. According to the probabilistic results, a relatively wider sampling range was obtained using Model-1 as compared to Model-2. In both material models, the variation in the fiber volume ratio (V_f) has an important effect on the variation of the output parameter U2. For Model-1, the most sensitive parameter is found to be the total volumetric shrinkage of the resin (V_{sh}) for S11 and U2. On the other hand, the most sensitive parameter is found to be the fully cured resin modulus ($E_{r\infty}$) and the fiber volume ratio (V_f) for S11 and U2, respectively, by using Model-2. Similarly, the effect of the variation in the V_f on S11 is less than on U2 for both models. On the other hand, the variation in $E_{r\infty}$ has a more important effect on S11 as compared to U2.

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